

Tumor cell derived osteopontin and prostaglandin E2 synergistically promote the expansion of myeloid derived suppressor cells during the tumor immune escape phase

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ABSTRACT

The immune escape stage in cancer immunoediting is a pivotal feature, transitioning immune-controlled tumor dormancy to progression, and augmenting invasion and metastasis. Tumors employ diverse mechanisms for immune escape, with generating immunosuppressive cells from skewed hematopoiesis being a crucial mechanism. This led us to suggest that tumor cells with immune escape properties produce factors that induce dysregulations in hematopoiesis. In support of this suggestion, this study found that mice bearing advanced-stage tumors exhibited dysregulated hematopoiesis characterized by the development of splenomegaly, anemia, extramedullary hematopoiesis, production of immunosuppressive mediators, and expanded medullary myelopoiesis. Further *ex vivo* studies exhibited that conditioned medium derived from EL4Luc2 cells could mediate the expansion of myeloid derived suppressor cells (MDSCs) in bone marrow cell cultures. The protein array profiling results revealed the presence of elevated levels of osteopontin (OPN), prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) and interleukin 17 (IL-17) in the culture medium derived from EL4Luc2 cells. Accordingly, substantial levels of these factors were also detected in the sera of mice bearing EL4Luc2 tumors. Among these factors, only PGE2 alone could increase the number of MDSCs in the BM cell cultures. This effect of PGE2 was significantly potentiated by the presence of OPN but not IL-17. Finally, *in vitro* treatment of EL4Luc2 cells with pioglitazone, a modulator of OPN and cyclooxygenase 2 (COX-2) resulted in a significant reduction in cell proliferation in EL4Luc2 cells. Our findings highlight the significant role played by tumor cell-derived OPN and PGE2 in fostering the expansion of medullary MDSCs and in promoting tumor cell proliferation. Furthermore, these intertwined cancer processes could be key targets for pioglitazone intervention.

1. Introduction

The concept of cancer immunoediting has been proposed to describe the interactive process between the immune system and developing tumors. This process consists of three successive phases: elimination, equilibrium, and escape [1,2]. The elimination phase considers that most of the newly transformed cells express antigenic structures which are different from their parental cells [3]. Thus, they can be recognized and effectively eliminated by both the innate and adaptive immune effector cells, leading to the eradication of developed tumor cells [1–3].

The equilibrium phase describes a condition in which certain transformed cell variants that possess a less, or non-immunogenic phenotype manage to survive the elimination phase and thus, continue to grow [1,2,4]. However, during this phase, immune-mediated dormancy prevents the outgrowth of tumor cells. It is during the equilibrium phase that tumor antigen-specific T cells exert tumor growth arrest by providing a balance between anti-tumor cytokines (interleukin-12 (IL-12) and interferon-gamma (IFN-gamma)) and pro-tumor cytokines (IL-10 and IL-23) [4,5].

In the escape phase, tumor cells that have gained the ability to evade

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immune recognition/elimination arise as continuously growing cells and form a visible malignant tumor [1,2]. The escape phase is considered a hallmark trait of cancer and can develop via two main alternative and/or coinciding mechanisms [4–6]. First, to avoid immune recognition, tumor cells may change their geno-phenotypes by down-regulating the expression of MHC class I, and/or up-regulating the expression of the immunoinhibitory molecules such as programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) [4,6,7]. As the second mechanism, tumor cells may establish an immunosuppressive status comprising several immunosuppressive cells within the tumor microenvironment (TME) as well as systemically [4,6,7]. These immunosuppressive cells include granulocytic and monocytic myeloid-derived immunosuppressive cells (G-MDSCs and M-MDSCs, respectively), regulatory T-cells (Tregs), regulatory B cells, and erythroid progenitor cells (EPCs) which in a concerted manner, not only suppress the immune responses against the developed tumor but also provide a condition for tumor progression and metastasis [4,6–8]. These cells exert their immunosuppressive effects either by producing immunomodulatory soluble factors (e.g., vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), interleukin 10 (IL-10), transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β), prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), arginases, and indoleamine-pyrrole 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO)) or through the expression of cell surface immune inhibitory receptors such as PD-L1 [4,6–8].

Among the immunosuppressive cells, MDSCs and EPCs have been abundantly found in the TME and are considered highly effective regulators of immune responses [8–10]. It has been postulated that these cells emerge due to dysregulated hematopoiesis [8–10]. Concerning MDSCs, studies have revealed that they are generated in the bone marrow and spleen through a phenomenon known as emergency myelopoiesis [10]. Several factors, such as granulocyte-macrophage colony stimulating factor (GM-CSF), granulocyte colony stimulating factor (G-CSF), macrophage colony stimulating factor (M-CSF), PGE2 and IL-6 are believed to mediate this phenomenon [10]. On the other hand, the generation of EPCs can be attributed to an ineffective medullary erythropoiesis which leads to the expansion of these cells in the extramedullary sites [8].

In light of the aforementioned information, it is now well established that dysregulations in myelopoiesis and erythropoiesis can be considered as fundamental mechanisms in the immune escape phase of cancer immunoeediting. However, the extent to which tumor cells and their produced molecules *per se* contribute to the emergence of these dysregulations remains largely unexplored. For a better clarification of this issue, we hypothesize that any cancer cell variant that has already entered the immune escape phase can also skew hematopoiesis towards immunosuppressive myelopoiesis via the production of secretory factors (free molecules and/or extracellular vesicles). This study was designed to investigate this hypothesis employing a T-lymphoma murine model.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM), RPMI 1640 medium, Dulbecco's phosphate buffer saline (DPBS), heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), sodium pyruvate, L-glutamine, 2-mercaptoethanol, penicillin and streptomycin (PEST) and mouse recombinant IL-17A were obtained from ThermoFisher (ThermoFisher Scientific, Stockholm, Sweden). PGE2 and recombinant mouse osteopontin were purchased from Sigma (Sigma-Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and R&D Systems (Minneapolis, USA), respectively.

2.2. Cell culture

EL4 lymphoma cell line (referred to hereafter as EL4luc2 cells) was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (Manassas, VA, USA) and were stably engineered to express the gene, luc2 (PerkinElmer, MA, USA). The cells were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 10 %

FBS, 1 mM sodium pyruvate, 2 mM L-glutamine, 50 μ M β -mercaptoethanol, 100 units/ml penicillin, and 100 μ g/ml streptomycin (complete medium) at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO₂. The cells were routinely passaged every 3–4 days.

2.3. Mice

Female C57BL/6N (H-2^b) mice at 8–10 weeks of age were purchased from Charles River (Charles River Laboratories, Germany). The animals were kept in standard cages at 21–22 °C with a 12-h light/dark cycle and 50 % humidity at our animal facility (Karolinska University Hospital, NOVUM). All mice were given *ad libitum* access to irradiated standard mouse chow and tap water and allowed to acclimatise for one week before inoculation with tumor cells. All experiments in this study were pre-approved by the Stockholm Southern Ethics Committee for Animal Research and were conducted in accordance with the animal welfare law, the Animal Protection Regulation and the Regulation of the Swedish National Board for Laboratory Animals (approval number: S67-14).

2.4. Tumor induction, collection of blood and cell suspension from the bone marrow and spleen

Mice were injected subcutaneously (s.c.) in the loose skin of the neck with 5×10^5 EL4luc2 tumor cells in 100 μ l DPBS. Tumor volumes were evaluated daily by measuring two perpendicular diameters with a caliper. Tumor volume (V) was calculated using the following equation: $V = (W^2 \times L)/2$, where W is the width and L is the length, both in centimeters. A group of mice (n = 3–5) were left un-injected and used as the control group.

2.5. Collection of blood and single cell preparation from the bone marrow and spleen

When the tumor size reached to approximately 1.5 cm³, the experimental mice were bled by cardiac puncture under isoflurane anesthesia and euthanized by cervical dislocation. Spleens, livers, lymph nodes and long bones were removed. The spleens were divided, with one part suspended in DPBS after being teased apart. Bone marrow cells were flushed from the bones and suspended in DPBS. All collected cells were washed and resuspended in DPBS.

Blood samples were collected in EDTA dipotassium tubes (Microtainer, BD Bioscience, NJ, USA) or clotting tubes. Serum was obtained from the latter tubes after centrifugation and stored at –20 °C.

2.6. Hematological analysis and measurement of cell viability

The total white blood cell count and differential blood cell count were performed as described previously [11,12]. In a non-cyanide procedure, the alkaline hematin method was used to measure the concentration of hemoglobin in the blood samples as described previously [13].

In all cases, cell viability was assessed by quantifying the number of living cells using the trypan blue assay.

2.7. Histological analysis of the spleen

Spleen sections (4–5 μ m) were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and examined by light microscopy (ZEISS, Carl Zeiss, AG, Germany). The images obtained were converted to an EGB color format with the Adobe Photoshop CS4 program (Adobe systems, San Jose, CA, USA).

2.8. Collection of EL4luc2 conditioned media

EL4Luc2 cells were cultured in complete DMEM medium as

described above and incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO₂ for 8 days. After that, the cell culture medium was separated from the cells using serial centrifugation steps: 700g for 5 min, 2000g for 10 min, and 3000g for 20 min. Then, the obtained cells- and debris-free conditioned medium was filtered through a 0.22 µm filter.

2.9. *Ex vivo* co-culture of bone marrow cells with EL4luc2 cell-conditioned medium and live cell imaging assays

For *ex vivo* co-culture, bone marrow (BM) cells from the femur and tibia of female C57BL/6N (H-2b) mice were isolated and seeded in a 24 well plate at a concentration of 75 x10⁵ cells per well in 500 µl of either EL4luc2 cell conditioned-medium or control complete medium. Thereafter, the culture plate was placed in a humidified incubator equipped with an Incucyte® Live-Cell Analysis System (Incucyte® S3). Live Cell Analysis System, Sartorius Lab Instruments GmbH & Co, KG, Goettingen, Germany). Live cell imaging was performed for eight day as described previously [14]. Incucyte data was analyzed using Incucyte software (v2019B). GraphPad Prism version 9.0 was used to generate graphs and perform statistical analysis.

2.10. Co-culture of bone marrow cells with prostaglandin E2, osteopontin and interleukin 17

BM cells at a concentration of 1x10⁶/mL were suspended in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10 % FBS and 2-ME (5 × 10⁻⁵ M) and plated into the wells of 24-well flat-bottom culture plates (Costar, Corning Incorporated, Corning NY, USA) in the presence or absence of PGE2 (10 ng/ml), OPN (1 mg/ml), IL-17 and/or a combination of PGE2 (10 ng/ml) and OPN (1 mg/ml), PGE2 and IL-17 and/or OPN and IL-17. Cell cultures were incubated for 72 h at 37 °C under a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO₂.

2.11. Measurement of arginase and indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase

The arginase activity in the serum samples and cell culture supernatants was quantified employing a commercially available kit (Sigma–Aldrich, Stockholm, Sweden) in accordance with the manufacturer’s instruction.

The IDO activity in the serum samples was determined spectrophotometrically, as previously described [15].

2.12. Measurement of prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), osteopontin (OPN) and interleukin 17 (IL-17) and IL-10

The levels of PGE2, OPN and IL-17 in the cell culture supernatants and serum samples were quantified using commercially available ELISA kits (Mouse Prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) ELISA Kit, MyBioSource, Inc. San Diego, CA, USA, Mouse/Rat Osteopontin (OPN) Quantikine ELISA Kit, R&D Systems, Abingdon, UK, and ELISA Flex: Mouse IL-17A (HRP), Mabtech AB, Nacka Strand, Sweden), in accordance with the manufacturers’ instructions.

The levels of IL-10 in the sera were quantified employing a commercially available ELISA kit (Mouse IL-10 ELISA Ready-SET-Go® (eBioscience, San Diego, CA, USA), in accordance with the manufacturer’s instruction.

2.13. Proteomic profiling of angiogenesis factors

The relative expression levels of 31 proteins associated with mouse angiogenesis in the cell culture supernatants and/or serum samples were visualized using a proteome profiler mouse angiogenesis array kit (R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA). The assay was performed in accordance with the manufacturer’s instructions. Pixel color densities on the membranes were analyzed using the image analysis software, ImageJ.

2.14. Proteomic profiling of cytokines and chemokines

The relative expression levels of 40 murine cytokines and chemokines in the cell culture supernatants and/or serum samples were determined using a proteome profiler mouse cytokine array kit, Panel A (R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA). The assay was performed in accordance with the manufacturer’s instruction, Pixel color densities on the membranes were analyzed using the image analysis software, ImageJ.

2.15. Immunofluorescent staining and flow cytometric analysis

Immunophenotyping of BM and spleen cells was performed using a panel of antibodies against the appropriate murine cell surface antigens. The antibodies employed were the following: anti-mouse Gr1 antibody labeled with (–) R-phycoerythrin (PE) (clone RB6-8C5, Cat. No: 553128), rat anti-mouse CD11b antibody labeled with (–) (APC) (clone M1/70, Cat. No: 553312), rat anti-mouse CD19-PE (clone 1D3, Cat. No: 557399), rat anti-mouse CD8a-PE (clone 53–6.7, Cat. No: 561095), rat anti-mouse CD4-PerCP (clone RM 4–5, Cat. No: 561090), rat anti-mouse CD9-Alexa Flour 647 (clone KMC8, Cat. No: 564233), rat anti-mouse CD71 labelled PE (clone C2, Cat. No: 553262), and rat anti-mouse TER 119 labelled APC (clone TER 119, Cat. No: 651033) (all antibodies were from Pharmingen, BD Biosciences, Stockholm, Sweden). The cells were stained with labelled antibodies in accordance with the recommendations of the manufacturer. The stained cells were analyzed utilizing a FACSArray flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson, San Jose, CA). For each sample, the data from 10,000 events (individual cells) were collected and analyzed using the CellQuest Software.

2.16. Cell viability assay

EL4-Luc 2 cells were seeded in 96-well plates at the density of 1 x 10⁴ cells/well and treated with increasing concentrations of pioglitazone from 50 µM to 500 µM [16]. Thereafter, the plates were incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO₂. After 3, 4 and 5 days of incubation, the cells were then incubated for 4 h with WST-1 reagent (Sigma-Merck, Stockholm, Sweden) at 37 °C, and the absorbance of WST formazan dye was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader (SpectraMax i3X, Molecular Devices, San Jose, CA, USA). Cell viability was calculated as the percentage of viable cells relative to that in the untreated sample.

2.17. Expression of the data and statistical analysis

Data are presented as means ± standard deviation (SD). Depending on the experiment, statistical analysis was performed using either a two-tailed Student’s *t*-Test or the Mann–Whitney test (*U* test) or one-way ANOVA test. A *p*-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed with GraphPad Prism9 software. For the ANOVA and *t* tests, statistically significant *p* values were represented as follows:

* *p* < 0.05, ** *p* < 0.01, ****p* < 0.001.

2.18. Data availability

The data generated in this study are available within the article. Derived are available from the corresponding author upon request.

3. Results

3.1. Necroscopic features of EL4luc2 lymphoma mice during the emergence of immune escape phase

Inoculation of female C57BL/6 mice with EL4luc2 cells resulted in the development of visible advanced tumors (tumor size

approximately 1.5 cm^3) within 11 days (Fig. 1a). At necropsy, the tumor-bearing mice showed enlargements of the spleen, liver, and inguinal lymph nodes, along with the pallor of the long bones as compared to those of control tumor free mice (Fig. 1b-e).

3.2. Immune escape phase of EL4luc2 lymphoma coincides with a dysregulated hematopoiesis in the spleen and bone marrow

The immune escape phase of EL4luc2 lymphoma is associated with dysregulated hematopoiesis in the spleen and bone marrow. Previous studies revealed an expansion of splenic and circulatory MDSCs, which are highly sensitive to specific myeloablative cytostatic drugs [11,12]. This observation, along with splenomegaly in EL4luc2-bearing mice, suggested the occurrence of extramedullary hematopoiesis during the tumor immune escape phase. To investigate this further, we conducted flow cytometric and histologic analyses on the spleen. Fig. 2a demonstrates a significant increase in the numbers of granulocytes (Gr1 +), macrophages (CD11b +), total MDSCs (CD11 + Gr1 +), EPCs (including CD71 + and CD71+/TER119 + subpopulations), B cells (CD19 +), regulatory B cells (CD19+/CD9 +), helper T cells (CD4 +), cytotoxic T cells (CD8 +), and erythrocytes (TER119 +) in the spleens of EL4luc2 tumor-bearing mice compared to tumor-free control mice. Additionally, EL4luc2 tumor-bearing mice exhibited higher frequencies of granulocytes, total MDSCs, and late EPCs but lower frequencies of B cells, helper T cells, cytotoxic T cells, and erythrocytes (Fig. 2b and c). Histopathological examination of the spleen confirmed these findings, with both red and white pulps showing hypercellularity in mice with EL4luc2 tumors compared to control mice (Fig. 2d and e). Specifically, the splenic red pulp exhibited increased numbers of erythropoietic foci, maturing myeloid cells, and megakaryocytes in tumor-bearing mice (Fig. 2d). The splenic white pulp was also enlarged and had higher cellularity in the same animals (Fig. 2d and e).

The pale appearance of the long bones in EL4luc2 tumor-bearing mice also suggested a skewed hematopoiesis in this primary immune organ. Thus, to investigate this suggestion, we conducted immunophenotypic analysis on the BM cells using flow cytometry. The results obtained revealed substantial increases in both the total numbers and frequencies of G-granulocytes (Gr1 +), total MDSCs (CD11+/Gr1 +), and regulatory B cells (CD19+/CD9 +) in EL4luc2 tumor-bearing mice compared to the control group. Conversely, mice with tumors displayed significant reductions in the total numbers and frequencies of B cells (CD19 +) and cells within the erythroid lineage, including early and late EPCs and mature red blood cells (CD71+, CD71+/TER119+, and TER119 + cells, respectively) (Fig. 3a-c).

The alterations in hematopoietic cells in both the spleen and BM also had an impact on blood parameters. For instance, there was a slight

increase in the total number of white blood cells increased slightly (Fig. 3d) and the frequency of neutrophils significantly rose in tumor-bearing mice compared to tumor-free counterparts (Fig. 3e). Furthermore, the blood hemoglobin levels in the tumor-bearing mice were significantly lower than those in control mice (Fig. 3f).

Having observed that the numbers of splenic myeloid and erythroid progenitor cells, and regulatory B cells were significantly elevated during the immune escape phase of EL4luc2 lymphoma, we next sought to determine whether these elevations could generate an immunosuppressive status in their host. To investigate this, we measured the circulatory levels of arginase, IDO and IL-10 as the main immunosuppressive soluble factors produced by MDSCs and EPCs [8-10]. As depicted in Fig. 3g-j, serum levels of these factors were significantly higher in mice with EL4luc2 tumors than those in control animals.

Up-ward and down-ward triangles indicate increases or decreases in the respective values.

3.3. Tumor cell-derived secretory factors contribute to the expansion of bone marrow-derived MDSCs

The co-development of the immune escape phase of EL4luc2 with the extensive expansion of both granulocytes and total MDSCs in the bone marrow prompted us to further verify our above-mentioned hypothesis by testing whether secreted factors present in conditioned medium from EL4luc2 cells can modify the process of hematopoiesis in the bone marrow cells. Upon employing a live cell imaging and analysis system, we found that in comparison to the control medium, conditioned medium from EL4luc2 cells were able to increase the cell confluency (Fig. 4a and b, Fig. 4c, respectively) as well as the frequency of total MDSCs (Gr1+/CD11b + cells) by more than 25 % (Fig. 4a and b, Fig. 4c, respectively).

3.4. Osteopontin, prostaglandin E2, and interleukin 17 are secreted by EL4luc2 cells and are elevated during the immune escape phase of EL4luc2 lymphoma

We next performed protein array profiling to identify the nature of secretory factors produced by EL4luc2 cells. Several factors including osteopontin (OPN), C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 12 (CXCL12), IL-16 and IL-17 were detected in the EL4luc2 cell culture medium (Fig. 5a and b). Among these factors, OPN has been shown to promote extramedullary myelopoiesis [17] and to activate the COX-2/PGE2 signaling pathway [18], which in turn induces the production of PGE2 [18], a non-protein factor that in the presence of GM-CSF, promotes the differentiation of medullary MDSCs [19]. Furthermore, IL-17 has been

Fig. 1. Tumor development and necropsy characteristics of mice bearing advanced stage EL4luc2 tumors. Female C57BL/6N mice were either un-injected (control, n = 5) or injected with EL4luc2 cells (n = 5). Tumor sizes were monitored until the advanced stage (a). Livers (b), spleens (c), and lymph nodes (d) were removed and weighed. (d) Long bones were examined for the color change (arrows). Statistical analysis was performed using Mann-Whitney U test (* $P \leq 0.05$).

Fig. 2. Accumulation of immunosuppressive MDSCs, EPCs, and enhanced extramedullary hematopoiesis in the spleen during advanced tumor development. (a and b), The spleens of C57BL/6N mice bearing an advanced stage of EL4luc2 tumors and their corresponding tumor free controls were analyzed for the total numbers (a) and frequencies (b) of different cell populations using flow cytometry. (c), Representative flow cytometric analysis of spleen cells for the myeloid, erythroid, B and T cells. (d and e) Representative microscopic (H&E staining) photographs (magnifications 200 and 400) of the spleen from a tumor free mouse (d) and a mouse with an advanced EL4luc2 tumor (e). Yellow arrowheads: erythroblastic foci, yellow arrows (megakaryocytes and short green arrows: myeloid cells. Splenic white pulp areas (dashed and dotted areas in d and e). Statistical analysis was performed using Mann-Whitney *U* test (**P* ≤ 0.05).

Fig. 3. Mice bearing advanced EL4luc2 tumors exhibit aberrant medullary myelopoiesis and anemia, along with elevated levels of circulating immunosuppressive factors (a and b), bone marrow of C57BL/6N mice bearing advanced EL4luc2 tumors and tumor free controls were subjected to flow cytometry analysis. (c), Representative flow cytometric analysis of bone marrow cells for the expression of myeloid (Gr1/CD11b), erythroid (CD71/TER119) and B (CD19/CD9) cell lineages. (d-f), Blood samples were examined for white blood cell count, complete differential count, and hemoglobin concentration. (g-j) Serum levels of arginase (g), IDO, (i), and IL-10 (j) were quantified using colorimetric assays (arginase and IDO) or ELISA (IL-10). Statistical analysis was performed using Mann-Whitney *U* test (**P* ≤ 0.05).

shown to indirectly affect hematopoiesis by stimulating granulopoiesis [20]. Thus, OPN, PGE2, and IL-17 levels were quantified in EL4luc2 cell culture medium and mice bearing EL4luc2 tumors. As demonstrated in

Fig. 6 a and b, both preparations showed elevated levels of OPN, PGE2 and IL-17 compared to controls (Fig. 5c-e, respectively).

Fig. 4. EL4Luc2 cell-derived soluble factors promote the survival and expansion of MDSCs in bone marrow cells. Freshly flushed bone marrow (BM) cells were cultured in a 24-well cell culture plate for 8 days using either a cell culture medium collected from EL4-Luc2 cells or a control medium. Subsequently, flow cytometry analysis was conducted on the cultured BM cells. (a) The kinetics of cell proliferation and survival of cultured BM cells monitored using the Incucyte® Live-Cell Analysis System. (b) Representative photographs of cultured BM cells after 8 days are presented. (c) Flow cytometric analysis of cultured BM cell on day 8 was performed to assess the expression of myeloid cell lineages. Representative photographs of this lineage are displayed above MDSCs bars. Statistical analysis was performed using the Mann-Whitney *U* test (**P* ≤ 0.05).

Fig. 5. Increased production of osteopontin (OPN) and prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) in EL4Luc2 cells and associated tumor model. (a and b), Expression of angiogenic factors and cytokines produced by EL4Luc2 cells was screened using proteome profiler kits for mouse angiogenesis factors (a) and cytokines/chemokines (b). (c-e), levels of OPN and PGE2, and IL-17 were measured in the control culture medium (white bars: c, d, e) EL4 cells-derived cell culture medium (black bars: c, d, e) and sera from tumor free (control) mice (white bars: c, d, e), and EL4Luc2 tumor-bearing mice (black bars: c, d, e), respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using the Mann-Whitney *U* test (**P* ≤ 0.05).

3.5. Osteopontin and prostaglandin E2 act in synergy to support and maintain the survival and expansion of myeloid derived immunosuppressive cells

Finally, we investigated the role of OPN, PGE2, and IL-17 in inducing aberrant medullary myelopoiesis in mice with advanced EL4Luc2 tumors. Bone marrow cells were cultured with or without these factors alone or

in combination for three days. As shown in Fig. 6a, the addition of PGE2 alone increased cell viability and the total number of MDSCs, along with slight, insignificant increase of arginase activity. Furthermore, the addition of OPN with PGE2 enhanced these effects (Fig. 6a-d). However, IL-17 did not affect cell viability or total MDSCs expansion induced by PGE2, and it had no significant effect on total MDSCs production (Fig. 6d and e). These results suggest that OPN and PGE2 derived from cancer

Fig. 6. Osteopontin (OPN) and prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) synergistically induce myelopoiesis with immunosuppressive activity. (a-d) Freshly flushed bone marrow (BM) cells were cultured in a 24-well cell culture plate for 72 h in the presence of various combinations of PGE2, OPN, and IL-17. Subsequently, cell viability (a and d) and immunophenotypic analysis of myeloid cells (b and e) flow cytometry analyses were conducted on the cultured BM cells using trypan blue exclusion test and flow cytometry, respectively. Representative photographs of myeloid cell populations are displayed above respective bars (b and e). c) Conditioned medial levels of arginase were quantified using colorimetric assays after treating BM cells with PGE2 and OPN. f) Effect of pioglitazone on the inhibition of proliferation of EL4 cells. Statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA test (* $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$).

cells synergistically promote the production of MDSCs in BM cells. Furthermore, it was shown that adding OPN and PGE2 to BM cells resulted in increased activity of arginase (Fig. 6c). These results suggest that possibly production of OPN by EL4luc2 cells has potentiated the expression of the COX-2 gene which in turn enhances the production of PGE2. Thus, it is likely that any treatment modalities that interfere with the production of OPN could suppress the production of PEG2 and even interferes with the cell proliferation. To evaluate this likelihood, we used pioglitazone, a modulator of OPN, to evaluate its effect on the proliferation of EL4luc2 cells. As shown in Fig. 6f, pioglitazone significantly inhibited the proliferation of EL4luc2 cells in a dose-dependent manner.

4. Discussion

In the current investigation, we conducted experiments to validate the hypothesis that cancer cell variants that have entered the immune escape phase of cancer immunoediting produce factors capable of inducing dysregulated hematopoiesis with immunosuppressive properties. By using the late stage of murine EL4luc2 lymphoma model, we considered that almost all the tumor cells that can grow *in vitro* and causing tumor *in vivo* particularly in immunocompetent hosts have already entered the immune escape phase. Thus, they can be employed as perfect models to study which cancer cell products can contribute to the induction of immune escape phase and dysregulated hematopoiesis. Based on this consideration, the immune escape phase fully develops when the tumor is visible, and the tumor cells have expanded in such a way that their products can research the distant immune organs to exert

their modulating and/or suppressive activities [4]. We first sought to map the pattern of hematopoiesis dysregulation in the model. At the time of the immune escape phase, tumor bearing mice had several necroscopic characteristics indicative of the presence of severe disturbances in the hematopoietic system. For instance, they exhibited splenohepatomegaly, a feature representing the development of EMH in cancer [21–23]. Evidence for the presence of EMH were the findings the numbers of myeloid progenitors, regulatory B cells, as well as different subpopulations of erythroid progenitors were significantly increased in the spleens of mice with advanced EL4luc2 tumors. Furthermore, the same organ showed typical histopathological characteristics of EMH, i. e., the red pulp was highly populated with erythropoietic foci along with increased numbers of myeloid cells and megakaryocytes. Interestingly, the splenic white pulp in the tumor bearing mice was also enlarged and exhibited hypercellularity. This observation along with the flow cytometric findings that the absolute numbers of splenic B and T cells (including both helper and cytotoxic subpopulations) were markedly increased in mice with EL4luc2 tumor suggests that like the red pulp, the splenic white pulp goes through significant alteration. In line with this suggestion, elevated numbers of splenic B and T cells have also been demonstrated in several other tumor models [24–27]. Thus, it is of high importance to characterize the functions as well as the role of these cells in the development of the immune escape phase of cancer immunoediting.

In EL4luc2 tumor bearing mice, the paleness of long bones along with the reduced numbers of cells belonging to the erythroid lineage clearly indicate that the medullary erythropoiesis is impaired in these animals. In fact, the expansion of EPCs in the spleen and anemia can

develop in these animals because of this impairment. On the other hand, substantial increases in the number of cells belonging to the myeloid lineage particularly, MDSCs indicate that the development of skewed medullary myelopoiesis is the primary factor contributing to the inhibition of erythropoiesis in the BM.

Tumor-induced immunosuppressive cells, specifically MDSCs and EPCs, exert their immunosuppressive effects by producing and releasing factors like arginase, IDO, and IL-10 [4,6–8]. In line with this, levels of these immunomodulatory factors were found to be increased during the immune escape phase of EL4luc2 tumor development. These elevations, along with the decrease in the number of splenic B and T cells, strongly suggests that dysregulated hematopoiesis in this lymphoma model leads to significant immunosuppression. Our transwell study revealed that EL4luc2 cells, in the absence of direct contact, induced the production of arginase-producing MDSCs in BM cells. This finding provides strong evidence that secreted factors, rather than cell–cell contact, play a role in triggering immunosuppressive myelopoiesis in the BM. Further investigation identified IL-16 and IL-17 as the most abundant cytokines secreted, and CXCL12 and OPN as the primary angiogenic factors released by EL4luc2 cells. While IL-16 is primarily known for its chemoattractant and T cell activation regulatory functions [28], its role in hematopoiesis is not well-established. However, increased expression of IL-16 has been associated with certain cancer types like cutaneous T cell lymphoma (CTCL), where it promotes malignant T cell proliferation [28]. Therefore, it is plausible that in EL4luc2 cells (as T lymphoma cells), IL-16 facilitates proliferation activities, although further research is needed to confirm this.

IL-17, a proinflammatory cytokine primarily produced by Th17 helper cells, has been suggested to indirectly increase the number of granulocytes in bone marrow cell cultures by inducing IL-6 production [20,29]. Binding to its receptor, IL-17R, IL-17 triggers the production of various inflammatory chemokines (e.g., CXCL1 and CXCL5) and cytokines (e.g., IL-6, G-CSF, and IL-8), leading to the recruitment of immunosuppressive cells [30]. While our *in vitro* studies did not establish a significant role for IL-17 in MDSC development, it is likely that EL-4luc2 cells exploit the inflammatory properties of IL-17 to attract immunosuppressive cells to the TME. Further research is necessary to investigate this possibility.

CXCL12, also known as stromal-derived factor 1 (SDF-1) is a homeostatic chemokine widely expressed in different tissues and is essential for certain physiological processes such as embryogenesis and the retention of hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells in the BM [31,32]. Several studies have demonstrated that the overexpression of CXCL12 by tumor cells enhances their abilities to adhere to the matrix molecules and stromal cells in the TME, to promote tumor angiogenesis and metastasis and to recruit immunosuppressive cells to the tumor site [31–33]. Thus, it is conceivable that during the immune escape phase of EL4luc2 tumor development, the secretion of CXCL12 mainly facilitates properties for tumorigenesis and tumor growth.

OPN, a pleotropic pro-inflammatory cytokine, is highly expressed in various types of cancers, including brain tumors, lung, kidney, liver, ovarian, prostate, pancreas, colorectal, esophageal, and gastric cancers [34,35]. It plays a crucial role in cellular transformation of preneoplastic cells and drives tumor progression by promoting anti-apoptosis, angiogenesis, metastasis, and immune evasion [34–36]. Within the TME, OPN exhibits immunosuppressive activities through mechanisms such as suppressing the activation of cytotoxic T cells, recruiting and polarizing macrophages towards the M2 phenotype, upregulating PD-L1 expression in macrophages, and inducing COX-2 expression in tumor-associated macrophages [37–40]. Additionally, OPN activation of COX-2 in cancer cells leads to the production of the end-point metabolite PGE2 [18]. Our findings demonstrated the coexistence of OPN and PGE2 in both the culture supernatant of EL4luc2 cells and the sera of mice with EL4luc2 tumors. This observation suggests either constitutive overexpression of the COX-2 gene in EL4luc2 cells or an increased expression of OPN promoting COX-2-mediated PGE2 production in a paracrine or

autocrine manner.

Our finding that the addition of PGE2 to the cultured BM cells increased the numbers of MDSCs without affecting the total cell count, confirms the role of PGE2 as an inducer of MDSC differentiation [19]. Furthermore, we observed that the introduction of OPN to PGE2-exposed BM cells not only enhanced the MDSC-differentiation effect of PGE2, but also increased the overall cell survival. This finding strongly suggests that tumor derived OPN and PGE2 synergistically maintain the survival of medullary MDSC progenitors and promote their differentiation into MDSCs. While OPN likely functions as a survival-promoting factor by interacting with its receptors CD44 and integrin receptors on MDSC progenitors [35], PGE2 exerts its differentiation effects on these cells through the prostaglandin EP2 receptor (EP2R) [19]. In the context of cancer immunoediting, our findings support the notion that OPN alone contributes to the transition from the equilibrium phase to immune escape, while the combination of OPN and PGE2 drives the immune escape phase towards full immunosuppression.

In conclusion, we disclosed the synergic action of tumor cell derived OPN and PGE2 in mediating aberrant myelopoiesis along with suppression of erythropoiesis in the BM. This collaborative cation of OPN and PGE2 exacerbates the tumor-induced immunosuppressive milieu by inducing EMH, characterized by the accumulation of MDSCs and EPDs and the development of erythropoietic foci and decrement of the adaptive immune cells in the spleen. Our findings offer a fundamental basis for a combination therapy that simultaneously targets OPN and inhibits the COX-2/PGE2 signaling pathway.

Authors contributions

MA-V conceived the idea. MA-V, OPBW, SEA, MH, BS, and DRM designed the study. MA-V, DRM, SB, and DKM performed the experiments. MA-V wrote the manuscript. DRM, SB, DKM, OS, OPBW, BS, MH, and SEA assisted with writing the manuscript. All authors reviewed the manuscript and approved its final version.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Doste R Mamand: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Safa Bazaz:** Data curation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Visualization. **Dara K. Mohammad:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation, Visualization. **Osama Saher:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Oscar P. B. Wiklander:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing, Editing. **Behnam Sadeghi:** Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Moustapha Hassan:** Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Samir EL-Andaloussi:** Funding acquisition, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Manuchehr Abedi-Valugerdi:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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